

Multi-Horizon Direction of Arrival Forecasting with Temporal Fusion Transformers: A Time-Series Learning Approach to Target Tracking

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Abstract—This paper explores the application of Temporal Fusion Transformers (TFTs) to target recognition and multi-horizon tracking, with a particular emphasis on enhancing Direction of Arrival (DoA) estimation in complex signal environments. By leveraging the advanced temporal modeling capabilities and dynamic feature selection mechanisms inherent to the TFT architecture, we adapt and optimize the model for improved performance in antenna signal processing, leading to a more accurate and robust estimation framework. Our analysis underscores the architectural strengths of TFTs, especially their capacity to model long-range temporal dependencies and to dynamically prioritize sensor-derived features—capabilities that are essential for precise target tracking and recognition. We train and evaluate the model under diverse conditions, including multi-horizon forecasting and varying prediction latencies across models. The proposed method is benchmarked against state-of-the-art algorithms, including recurrent neural networks and standard transformer-based models. Extensive experimental results demonstrate that the TFT-based approach consistently outperforms existing techniques in forecasting accuracy, multi-target recognition, and computational complexity, highlighting its potential to advance the field of DoA estimation.

Index Terms—Direction of arrival (DoA) estimation, temporal fusion transformer (TFT), array signal processing, machine learning for signal processing, forecasting, target recognition, target tracking

This research was supported by the European Union through the Horizon Europe Marie Skłodowska-Curie Staff Exchanges Programme “6G intelligent connectivity and interaction for users and infrastructures (6G-ICARUS)” under Grant no. 101131342. (Corresponding author: Constantinos M. Mylonakis)

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I. INTRODUCTION

Accurate and efficient target recognition and tracking remains a fundamental challenge across a range of engineering and signal processing applications, from the earliest forms of radar and sonar systems [1]–[3] to the latest advances in unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) [4]–[6] and autonomous vehicles [7]–[9]. Advancements in object tracking significantly enhance direction of arrival (DoA) estimation tasks by providing critical information about target location and movement, which is essential for accurately determining the angle of incoming signals at a sensor array. By tracking the movement of targets over time, systems enhanced by target tracking algorithms can refine DoA estimations, accounting for dynamic changes in the environment and reducing the uncertainty associated with single-timepoint measurements. Moreover, the integration of advanced tracking algorithms with DoA estimation enables more robust and reliable performance in complex scenarios, e.g., those involving multiple, closely spaced targets or non-stationary sources. This synergy between target recognition, tracking, and DoA estimation ultimately leads to more precise and actionable information, which is critical for a wide range of applications, including surveillance, autonomous vehicles, robotics, and remote sensing.

A. Literature Review

In earlier developments, target recognition and tracking relied heavily on deterministic algorithms and handcrafted features derived from sensor data. Kalman filters [10]–[12] and particle filters [13] were foundational in estimating the state of a target. While early Kalman filter formulations assumed linear system dynamics, subsequent extensions, e.g., extended Kalman filter (EKF), unscented Kalman filter (UKF), and particle filters were developed to handle nonlinearities more effectively. As the complexity of both environments and targets increased, the need for more advanced methods capable of processing large volumes of data and making real-time decisions became evident. [10] introduces a recursive solution to the linear filtering problem of discrete data. For nonlinear systems, the introduction of the EKF [11] and later the UKF [12], which employs the unscented transformation to more accurately capture mean and covariance estimates, represented significant advances. Complementary to these developments, particle filters [13] offer an innovative approach for estimating

system states under nonlinear and non-Gaussian conditions, by using a set of particles to represent posterior distributions and updating them sequentially. For multi-target tracking, [14], introduces the joint probabilistic data association algorithm. [15] introduces the multiple hypothesis tracking (MHT) algorithm. MHT is recognized for its ability to maintain multiple hypotheses about target trajectories, offering robustness in cluttered environments where track ambiguities are common. Bayesian techniques for tracking are well represented in [16].

[17] introduces a kernel-based object tracking method using mean-shift. This method is robust to changes in object appearance but faces challenges with speed, scale, and rotation. [18] explores parallel tracking mechanisms in visual perception. [19] proposes a high-speed tracking method using kernelized correlation filters (KCF), gaining recognition for its efficiency in real-time tasks, although it struggled with nonrigid objects and long-term tracking. [20] enhances KCF with adaptive correlation filters, improving appearance adaptation but still facing problems with long-term tracking and complex motions. [21] addresses these limitations by combining correlation filters with a re-detection mechanism, improving recovery from occlusion and extending tracking performance.

Recent advances in deep learning [22] for object tracking are exemplified by [23], which introduces CenterTrack, which predicts object locations as points. [24] lays the foundation for CNNs, now widely applied in tracking and signal processing. The work presented on [25] for RNNs and LSTMs remains pivotal for sequence modeling in temporal signal processing. [26] explores deep learning-based super-resolution for channel and DoA estimation in massive MIMO, targeting improved signal accuracy in vehicular scenarios, while [27] introduces a computationally efficient adaptive beamforming algorithm for coprime arrays and [28] develops a fast machine learning method for DoA recognition in vehicular communications. [29] proposes a machine learning model for DoA estimation and model order selection, leveraging subarray sampling to improve performance. A notable contribution to wideband estimation is presented in [30], where a frequency decomposition strategy is used within the GS-WSpSF framework to improve precision while maintaining computational feasibility. Similarly, [31] addresses the challenge of gain-phase errors in massive MIMO systems by developing a low-complexity approach tailored for coherently distributed sources. In [32], a residual attention network with transfer learning enhances gridless DoA estimation, improving generalization. Robust estimation techniques for impulsive noise conditions are introduced in [33], leveraging low-rank matrix approximation and weakly convex optimization to increase resilience against outliers. For vehicular applications, [34] exploits motion characteristics to improve DoA estimation with limited snapshots, crucial for the automotive MIMO radar.

Building on these, [35] presents a novel CNN-based 3D DoA estimation model, [36] proposes a framework for 5G NR positioning, [37] applies neural networks for underwater DoA estimation, and [38] improves multi-speaker DoA using audio-visual data. [39] introduces a dual-class token vision transformer for DoA estimation in low signal to noise ratio environments, demonstrating robustness in challenging condi-

tions. [40] presents TIPS, a transformer-based indoor positioning system using WiFi signals, enhancing accuracy but facing deployment challenges. [41] creates a fast object detection framework that excels in face detection but struggles with small objects. [42] proposes the TLD framework for real-time tracking, effective with occlusions but prone to errors with fast-moving objects, whereas [43] introduces deep residual learning, foundational in computer vision but computationally demanding. [44] presents YOLO, which achieves real-time object detection but faces difficulties with small objects in dense scenes. Finally, [45] explores graph-based reasoning networks for better scene understanding, resulting in high computational cost.

B. Motivation and Contributions

The introduction of transformer architectures has revolutionized the field of natural language processing and, more recently, has begun to impact the domains of computer vision and spatio-temporal modeling. Transformers [46], characterized by their self-attention mechanisms, have demonstrated remarkable success in capturing long-range dependencies and complex patterns in the data. Self-attention networks have allowed researchers to capture spatial dependencies between antenna arrays, leading to improved DoA estimation accuracy compared to traditional methods and various CNN-based approaches [35]–[40]. The attention mechanisms intrinsic to transformers are crucial for managing the high-dimensional data typical of wireless communication systems.

The temporal fusion transformer (TFT) is a notable extension of the transformer architecture, specifically designed for multi-horizon forecasting and time series analysis [47]. TFTs integrate the strengths of traditional transformers with additional innovations that enhance their ability to model temporal relationships and incorporate static covariates. Key innovations include the use of gated residual networks (GRNs) for the effective combination of static and dynamic features, as well as temporal attention mechanisms that allow the model to focus on the most relevant time steps for prediction. These characteristics make TFTs suitable for target recognition and tracking, where modeling temporal dynamics is critical. TFTs overcome limitations of earlier methods by offering a robust framework for handling complex, multimodal sensor data. Their ability to fuse features and attend to temporal patterns enables more accurate and reliable performance, even in scenarios with nonlinear target motion.

Despite the extensive advancements in DoA estimation models, a critical gap remains in leveraging forecasting techniques to enrich these systems. Forecasting future positions by analyzing historical target tracking data could offer a groundbreaking evolution in DoA estimation. The integration of time series forecasting would allow for proactive adjustments, enabling the system to anticipate target movements and adapt in real-time. By combining time series forecasting with spatial awareness, this approach can improve both accuracy and response times, particularly in scenarios involving occlusions, signal noise, or rapid directional shifts. Iterative forecasting methods assume that all variables except the target

are known at the time of prediction, simplifying the process by feeding only the target variable into future inputs. This approach is limited in real-world scenarios where various time-varying inputs—often unknown in advance—are crucial for accurate outcomes. In contrast, TFTs effectively address this complexity by integrating diverse inputs, combining static covariates with past-observed and future-known time-varying variables.

In this research, we explore the application of TFTs to the problem of target recognition and tracking. To the best of the authors' knowledge, this is the first time time series analysis has been applied to enhance DoA estimation and address the challenges of prediction time and array signal processing. The key contributions of this study are:

- First, we customize the TFT architecture to meet the specific needs of target tracking applications. This adaptation involves not only the preprocessing of sensor array data, but also the integration of relevant features that enhance the model's ability to interpret complex data patterns effectively. We establish a principled connection between classical signal modeling and deep learning-based prediction by deriving input features for the TFT model from physical DoA signal characteristics. In addition, we generate the dataset for our analysis using sensor data, simulating motion in 3D space for three different target types.
- Next, we carry out a series of comprehensive experiments to rigorously assess the performance of the proposed TFT in a wide range of scenarios. These scenarios include variations in noise levels, interference conditions, and dynamic environments, allowing us to evaluate the model's robustness and adaptability in real-world applications. Moreover, we perform a detailed comparative analysis of the presented results with conventional tracking methods and state-of-the-art machine learning approaches.
- Finally, we conduct a thorough investigation into the interpretability of the TFT's predictions, providing in-depth insights into the model's decision-making process and enabling a clear understanding of how different factors influence the model's output.

C. Structure

The following sections are organized as follows: In Section II we provide a detailed analysis of the dataset employed in our study, together with the signal model essential for antenna signal processing, and we introduce the proposed architecture designed for target tracking applications. Section III delves into the specifics of the TFT architecture, outlining its components, and highlighting its advantages. Section IV presents a thorough analysis of the TFT's performance across various target recognition and tracking scenarios, accompanied by experimental results and comparisons with state-of-the-art models. Finally, in Section V, we conclude by summarizing our key contributions and outlining potential avenues for future research to further advance the field.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

To establish a clear connection between the classical array-processing formulation and the feature construction used in our learning framework, we first outline the geometric and physical principles governing the received signals. These relationships form the mathematical basis from which the temporal and spatial features used by the TFT are derived.

A. Signal Model

In a three-dimensional (3D) framework, incoming signals are defined by angle pairs (θ_n, ϕ_n) , representing polar θ_n and azimuth ϕ_n of the spherical coordination system, for each signal $n = 1, \dots, N$, where N is the number of signals. To describe the orientation of the incoming wavefronts, we represent the spatial direction of these signals using spherical coordinates through the direction vector \mathbf{v}_n , expressed as:

$$\mathbf{v}_n = \cos \phi_n \sin \theta_n \mathbf{x}_0 + \sin \phi_n \sin \theta_n \mathbf{y}_0 + \cos \theta_n \mathbf{z}_0, \quad (1)$$

with $\mathbf{x}_0, \mathbf{y}_0, \mathbf{z}_0$ being unit vectors along the x, y, and z axes. This vector directly links the angular DoA parameters to the array geometry and serves as the starting point for deriving time delays and phase shifts.

The steering vector α_n is shaped by the time delays $\tau_m(\theta_n, \phi_n)$ for each signal. These delays determine how the incoming plane wave reaches different antenna elements and thus encode the spatial information used for DoA estimation. Accordingly, the propagation delay from the m th antenna element to the reference point is defined as

$$\tau_m(\theta_n, \phi_n) = \frac{\mathbf{r}_m \cdot \mathbf{v}_n}{c}, \quad m = 1, \dots, M, \quad (2)$$

where c is the speed of light, M is the number of antennas, and \mathbf{r}_m denotes the position vector of the m -th antenna element. This delay term later becomes a key temporal feature extracted for transformer-based learning.

Fig. 1. Antenna array with sensor-based target recognition scheme.

Using these delays, the steering vector α_n for the n -th signal—describing phase differences across array elements—is given by:

$$\alpha_n = \begin{bmatrix} \exp(j2\pi f_c \tau_1(\theta_n, \phi_n)) \\ \exp(j2\pi f_c \tau_2(\theta_n, \phi_n)) \\ \vdots \\ \exp(j2\pi f_c \tau_M(\theta_n, \phi_n)) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3)$$

where f_c is the carrier frequency. These phase shifts encode the spatial signature of each source. To jointly represent all incoming signals, we assemble the steering matrix \mathbf{A} as

$$\mathbf{A} = [\alpha_1 \quad \alpha_2 \quad \cdots \quad \alpha_N]. \quad (4)$$

This matrix forms the foundation of classical DoA estimation, beamforming, and subspace methods, and also serves as a conceptual bridge to the learned feature space used in our TFT framework. The received signals at the antenna array are modeled as

$$\mathbf{x}(k) = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{g}(k) + \mathbf{n}(k), \quad (5)$$

where $\mathbf{x}(k) \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times 1}$ represents the received vector, $\mathbf{g}(k) \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}$ denotes the source modulation, and $\mathbf{n}(k) \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times 1}$ is additive noise. This linear superposition expresses how spatial signatures (in \mathbf{A}) interact with temporal modulations (in $\mathbf{g}(k)$), a coupling that we later capture explicitly in the TFT temporal modeling. The spatial correlation matrix $\mathbf{R}_{xx} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times M}$ is defined as

$$\mathbf{R}_{xx} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{R}_{gg}\mathbf{A}^H + \mathbf{R}_{nn} = \mathbf{R}_{ss} + \mathbf{R}_{nn}, \quad (6)$$

where \mathbf{R}_{ss} is the signal component, \mathbf{R}_{gg} captures source temporal correlations, and \mathbf{R}_{nn} represents noise. This formulation clarifies how spatial and temporal structures jointly shape the observed data. Introducing the spatial correlation matrix at this stage is crucial as it characterizes the second-order statistics of the received array data, which underpin many classical DoA estimators such as MUSIC and ESPRIT. While our TFT-based framework does not operate directly on \mathbf{R}_{xx} , several of the spatial features used as transformer inputs—such as average received power, inter-element phase relationships, and temporal consistency of the spatial signature—are derived from or motivated by these statistical properties. Thus, the correlation matrix serves as a conceptual link between the deterministic propagation model and the feature representations provided to the learning architecture.

Finally, to link the signal-processing model to the learning architecture, we emphasize that incorporating time delays (τ_m) and other dynamic features is essential for prediction. These quantities provide temporally evolving covariates that the TFT exploits to model motion patterns and structural dependencies. By combining spatial features, temporal histories, and dynamic signal properties, the model strengthens robustness to noise, mobility, and multipath effects inherent in real-world array processing.

B. Data Model

In contemporary communication schemes, the dynamic movement of the receiver or transmitter affects key parameters such as Doppler shift and channel fading. These factors necessitate adaptive techniques to optimize communication performance. The Doppler effect, caused by relative motion between the transmitter and receiver, results in a frequency shift, which can be calculated using:

$$f_d = \frac{v}{c} f_c, \quad (7)$$

where v is the target's velocity, c is the speed of light, and f_c is the carrier frequency. In low-velocity scenarios, the shift is negligible, allowing standard frequency correction systems, e.g., phase-locked loops (PLLs), to handle minor deviations without significant signal degradation. However, for faster-moving targets (vehicles), Doppler shift becomes more pronounced, often ranging between 100–200 MHz for a 2 GHz carrier frequency. This can cause inter-carrier interference in orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) systems, reducing spectral efficiency. Recognizing and tracking Doppler-induced distortions enables the implementation of dynamic frequency tracking or advanced OFDM compensation techniques to maintain signal integrity. Signal strength P_r , which depends on the distance between the transmitter and receiver, follows the path loss equation:

$$P_r = P_t - (20 \log_{10}(d) + 20 \log_{10}(f_c) + 32.44), \quad (8)$$

where P_t is transmitted power, d is the distance, and f_c is the carrier frequency. For low-speed targets, gradual changes in distance result in minor variations in signal strength, which can be managed with power control mechanisms to ensure stable connectivity. In contrast, high-speed targets experience rapid changes in distance, leading to frequent signal fluctuations. DoA estimation helps accurately track the target's location, enabling precise beamforming. This technique directs transmission energy toward the target, compensating for movement and maintaining stronger communication links, even in fast-changing environments with significant Doppler shifts.

The fading behavior of a signal is influenced by both the speed of the moving target and the surrounding environment. For pedestrians moving at 1–3 m/s, fading is largely shaped by slow changes in the environment, resulting in dominant slow fading with occasional large-scale shadowing effects. Obstacles intermittently block the signal, causing gradual fluctuations in received strength. In contrast, UAVs moving at 5–20 m/s experience variable fading. The UAV is subject to variable fading conditions, with fast fading occurring intermittently during phases of high relative motion, and slow fading dominating during periods of hovering or steady movement. Rapid shifts in relative position and the resulting signal fluctuations require more robust signal processing, particularly under high mobility. Cars, typically traveling at 15–30 m/s, are primarily affected by fast fading. High-speed movement leads to frequent multipath and significant Doppler effects, causing rapid amplitude and phase variations. To maintain reliable communication in such conditions, advanced techniques like adaptive equalization and URLLC-based systems are used to ensure timely and stable data exchange. The fading assignments used in our synthetic data are intended as modeling proxies to facilitate controlled algorithmic evaluation, rather than definitive characterizations of real-world fading. These settings provide systematic stress-testing conditions, and we acknowledge that fading behavior for mobile targets such as UAVs may vary widely in practice, warranting more nuanced modeling in future studies.

The three mobility classes considered in this work, i.e., pedestrian, UAV, and ground vehicle (car), were selected due

to their established use in DoA estimation, RF localization, and movement-tracking literature. Each class represents a distinct Doppler and motion regime frequently employed to evaluate array-processing algorithms. Their relevance is supported by numerous studies, including pedestrian-based RF tracking [48], [49], UAV direction-finding and localization [50], [51], and vehicle-based array-sensor tracking and movement estimation [52], [53].

Fig. 2. Simulation of the movement of two targets over 1000 time steps, with monitoring of both θ and ϕ angles.

Incorporating target estimation and tracking algorithms into communication systems is highly beneficial for enhancing performance in dynamic environments. By accurately predicting the position and movement of a target, e.g., a walking individual, a UAV or a high-speed vehicle, the system can anticipate changes in Doppler shift, signal strength, and path loss more effectively. This allows for proactive adjustments to transmission parameters, reducing the impact of sudden signal degradation or frequency shifts. Target tracking also improves handover efficiency in cellular networks, as the system can forecast when a moving target will require a cell switch, thus preventing dropped connections and ensuring continuous, high-quality communication even under challenging conditions.

To implement a target recognition and tracking application utilizing the architecture of a TFT, the input data must be strategically structured to leverage the model’s strengths in handling both static and dynamic time series data. We do not incorporate the autocorrelation matrix R_{xx} , as its structure does not align with the sequential time-series input format required by the TFT. The TFT model is specifically designed to capture complex temporal dependencies directly from raw time-series data, rather than relying on second-order statistical measures, e.g., R_{xx} . Temporal inputs should encompass the evolving state of the target and its environment, including time-stamped positional data (polar and azimuth angles), velocity of angular change, distance from sensors, Doppler shift, and received power. This data captures critical

aspects of the target’s dynamics and signal characteristics. Static inputs include fixed attributes such as sensor type, target classification. These elements provide essential context for interpreting the temporal data. The target variable represents the future state to be predicted, which involves forecasting the target’s next angular position.

C. From Signal Model to TFT Input Features

To clarify the connection between the mathematical signal model and the learning architecture explicit, we outline the exact preprocessing pipeline used to construct the input features for the TFT. Each quantity derived in the signal model is mapped to either static, past-known, or past-observed covariates, as required by the TFT framework.

1) *Raw Array Measurements*: The complex array snapshots $\mathbf{x}(k) \in \mathbb{C}^M$ are decomposed into their real, imaginary, and phase components:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x}_{\text{real}}(k) &= \Re\{\mathbf{x}(k)\}, & \mathbf{x}_{\text{imag}}(k) &= \Im\{\mathbf{x}(k)\}, \\ \mathbf{x}_{\text{phase}}(k) &= \angle \mathbf{x}(k), \end{aligned}$$

yielding physically interpretable, real-valued features suitable for the transformer.

2) *Spatial Covariance Features*: To capture structural array information over short temporal windows, we compute the covariance based on Eq. (6) from which we extract the diagonal (power), leading eigenvalues, and principal eigenvectors. These features provide low-dimensional summaries of \mathbf{R}_{ss} and \mathbf{R}_{nn} and allow the TFT to learn spatial patterns without explicitly estimating \mathbf{A} .

3) *Model-Derived Temporal Features*: The physical quantities introduced in the signal model—time delays, directions, Doppler shifts, and received power—are used to form time-varying covariates:

- Time delays: $\tau_m(\theta_n, \phi_n)$
- Estimated Doppler from short-time frequency drift
- Signal strength: P_r , calculated on Eq. (8)
- Angular rate estimates: $\hat{\theta}(k), \hat{\phi}(k)$

These quantities allow the TFT to model kinematic evolution consistent with the signal model.

4) *Angular Target Labels*: To accommodate the circular geometry of angles, the ground-truth azimuth and polar are converted to sine–cosine form:

$$y_\theta(k) = [\sin \theta(k), \cos \theta(k)], \quad y_\phi(k) = [\sin \phi(k), \cos \phi(k)].$$

This representation avoids discontinuities at wrap-around boundaries and provides smooth regression targets.

5) *Mapping to TFT Input Groups*: Finally, the constructed features are assigned to the TFT’s input categories:

- **Static covariates**: antenna geometry, frequency band, target class.
- **Known future inputs**: Doppler predictions.
- **Observed past inputs**: real, imaginary and phase features, covariance summaries, received power, and derived temporal features.

This explicit mapping establishes a direct and practical bridge between the classical signal model and the TFT-based learning pipeline, ensuring that all model-derived features are grounded in physical array-processing principles.

TABLE I
STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF MOVEMENT PARAMETERS FOR DIFFERENT TARGET TYPES.

Statistic	Position (θ , ϕ)		θ Velocity	ϕ Velocity	Distance to Sensor	Doppler Shift	Received Power
	θ ($^\circ$)	ϕ ($^\circ$)					
Pedestrian (Slow Fading)							
Mean	60.80 $^\circ$	108.97 $^\circ$	0.03 $^\circ$ /s	-0.1 $^\circ$ /s	125.47 m	5.4 Hz	-93.43 dBm
Min	19.16 $^\circ$	48.20 $^\circ$	-0.5 $^\circ$ /s	-0.5 $^\circ$ /s	0 m	0 Hz	-138.14 dBm
Max	96.87 $^\circ$	184.92 $^\circ$	0.5 $^\circ$ /s	0.5 $^\circ$ /s	203.26 m	9 Hz	0 dBm
Std	19.35 $^\circ$	39.40 $^\circ$	0.11 $^\circ$ /s	0.11 $^\circ$ /s	41.83 m	1.2 Hz	3.74 dBm
Car (Fast Fading)							
Mean	-134.67 $^\circ$	-406.79 $^\circ$	-0.01 $^\circ$ /s	-0.14 $^\circ$ /s	546.65 m	120.8 Hz	-176.24 dBm
Min	-581.30 $^\circ$	-861.72 $^\circ$	-4.97 $^\circ$ /s	-5 $^\circ$ /s	0 m	0 Hz	-180.79 dBm
Max	225.27 $^\circ$	360.12 $^\circ$	5 $^\circ$ /s	4.82 $^\circ$ /s	871.81 m	160 Hz	0 dBm
Std	227.57 $^\circ$	300.54 $^\circ$	1.63 $^\circ$ /s	1.74 $^\circ$ /s	163.92 m	9.24 Hz	3.91 dBm
UAV (Moderate Fading)							
Mean	5.05 $^\circ$	0.42 $^\circ$	-0 $^\circ$ /s	0.05 $^\circ$ /s	14.97 m	18.9 Hz	-104.36 dBm
Min	-20 $^\circ$	-20 $^\circ$	-2.9 $^\circ$ /s	-3 $^\circ$ /s	0 m	0 Hz	-151.01 dBm
Max	20 $^\circ$	20 $^\circ$	3 $^\circ$ /s	3 $^\circ$ /s	28.28 m	30 Hz	0 dBm
Std	9.66 $^\circ$	11.94 $^\circ$	0.47 $^\circ$ /s	0.82 $^\circ$ /s	6.10 m	5.42 Hz	5.45 dBm

D. Dataset Creation

Our dataset simulates the dynamic movement of multiple targets over a span of X thousand seconds, with X representing a fixed number of samples collected simultaneously for all three target types: pedestrian, car, and UAV. Since each target type is recorded over X samples, the total dataset expands to $3 \times X$ rows. Each row contains seven columns of information, including θ , ϕ , velocity in θ , velocity in ϕ , distance to sensors, Doppler shift, and received power. Thus, the total dimensions of the dataset are $3 \times X$ rows and 7 columns. This parallel structure ensures consistent and synchronized data collection, allowing for comprehensive side-by-side comparisons of the movement patterns across all target types, which are then concatenated and analyzed collectively. The targets' positions are represented in spherical coordinates, with their movement defined by two angles: θ (polar) and ϕ (azimuth). For analyzing movement increments in θ (polar) and ϕ (azimuth), we can adopt varying degrees of change depending on the target type (pedestrian, car, UAV). Since pedestrians move slowly and change direction gradually, the increments in θ and ϕ should be small. A reasonable range is from -0.5 to 0.5 degrees per second. This low speed and minimal direction change keep the pedestrian's trajectory smoother, as expected in real-world scenarios.

Vehicles, on the other hand, move faster and can make sharper turns, especially on roadways. In this case, increments in θ and ϕ could range from -5 to 5 degrees per second, thus reflecting more significant changes in direction. UAVs have the capacity for sharp maneuvers in all directions. Depending on the type of UAV and its application, increments in θ and ϕ could range from -3 to 3 degrees per second, allowing for sharp and quick changes in direction. The overall range for both angles in the UAV testing is set from -20 to 20 degrees, which encompasses reasonable boundaries for directional changes in typical scenarios [54]. This differentiation in increments accurately simulates the behavior of various target types for tracking models, testing the TFT's ability to capture different patterns simultaneously, recognize distinct movement parameters, and produce accurate movement forecasts. A probabilistic model is incorporated

into the simulation to introduce realistic movement changes, significantly influencing the prediction and tracking accuracy of various models. This ensures the model can learn from regular, but not overly frequent, changes. These changes occur with a probability of 30%, every 5 seconds, adding an element of unpredictability that mimics real-world conditions, where movement trajectories are rarely linear or fully predictable.

To provide a comprehensive overview to the dataset, table I presents descriptive statistics for each variable in the dataset. Algorithm 1 is used to generate the dataset for subsequent analysis.

III. TFT ARCHITECTURE

TFTs are specifically designed for high-performance, interpretable multi-horizon forecasting. Their architecture comprises several key features that enhance performance, including gating mechanisms, variable selection networks, static covariate encoders, interpretable multi-head attention, and a decoder.

While the TFT provides a strong foundation for temporal modeling, its default configuration is not directly suited for tasks involving angular outputs and dynamic signal propagation. To adapt the model for the DoA estimation task, we introduce a series of architectural and methodological modifications that account for the spatial and temporal properties of antenna array signals. The model is restructured to accept angular measurements and signal-based covariates, including Doppler shift, received power, and distance from the sensor. These features are complemented by kinematic attributes like angular velocity and directional history. Given the circular nature of angular data, we apply sine and cosine transformations to represent elevation and azimuth angles, preserving continuity and periodicity during the learning process. This helps the model generalize across the full angular spectrum while avoiding artifacts near the boundaries. Moreover, we refine the TFT's variable selection mechanisms to better distinguish between static and time-varying inputs. Static features, such as target type or antenna configuration, are used to inform the model's internal gating functions and help condition predictions over time. In contrast, time-varying features capture dynamic aspects of the signal, including rapid motion and fading effects.

Algorithm 1 Simulation of Target Movement and Dataset Creation

- 1: **Initialization:**
 - 2: Define the number of timesteps X and the number of target types (3).
 - 3: Set the target types as: Pedestrian, Car, and UAV.
 - 4: Establish speed factors for each target type: 0.5 for pedestrians, 5 for cars, and 3 for UAVs.
 - 5: **Update Movement and Compute Parameters:**
 - 6: **for** $t = 2$ **to** 10000 **do**
 - 7: **for** each target i in $\{1, 2, 3\}$ **do**
 - 8: **if** $t \bmod 5 = 0$ **then**
 - 9: **if** a random event with a 30% probability indicates a direction change **then**
 - 10: Generate angle increments for θ and ϕ with opposite signs, influenced by the target's speed.
 - 11: **end if**
 - 12: **end if**
 - 13: Update the θ and ϕ angles based on the target's movement.
 - 14: Compute the velocities of the targets.
 - 15: Calculate the distance to the sensor using the updated θ and ϕ angles.
 - 16: Determine the received power and Doppler shift based on the computed parameters.
 - 17: **end for**
 - 18: **end for**
 - 19: **Prepare Dataset:**
 - 20: Extract the collected data for each target type.
 - 21: Consolidate all target data into a unified dataset of dimensions $3 \times X \times 7$ for subsequent analysis.
 - 22: Save the dataset.
-

This separation ensures that motion-invariant information is not conflated with fast-changing signal dynamics. Finally, we redesign the output and training objectives to support angular prediction. The quantile forecasting head is modified to return directional estimates for both elevation and azimuth, along with uncertainty bounds. The loss function is adapted to reflect the directional nature of the task, incorporating angular error penalties and temporal smoothness constraints.

A. Gating Mechanisms

Gating mechanisms are fundamental to the TFT as they adaptively manage the influence of different features and control the extent of non-linear processing. Gated residual network (GRN) is a core component that integrates primary inputs with optional context vectors, dynamically determining the relevance and contribution of each feature. GRN processes input \mathbf{a} and context \mathbf{c} as:

$$\text{GRN}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}) = \text{LayerNorm}(\mathbf{a} + \text{GLU}(\mathbf{h}_1)), \quad (9)$$

where

$$\mathbf{h}_1 = W_{1,\gamma}\mathbf{h}_2 + b_{1,\gamma}, \quad (10)$$

$$\mathbf{h}_2 = \text{ELU}(W_{2,\gamma}\mathbf{a} + W_{3,\gamma}\mathbf{c} + b_{2,\gamma}). \quad (11)$$

In these equations, $\text{LayerNorm}(\cdot)$ denotes layer normalization, which standardizes inputs to stabilize and accelerate training. $\text{ELU}(\cdot)$ activation function introduces non-linearity into the model, while \mathbf{h}_1 and \mathbf{h}_2 represent intermediate representations within the GRN. The matrices $W_{1,\gamma}$, $W_{2,\gamma}$, $W_{3,\gamma}$ and the biases $b_{1,\gamma}$, $b_{2,\gamma}$ are indexed by γ to enable weight sharing across layers.

Gated linear unit (GLU) further controls the contribution of the GRN's output:

$$\text{GLU}(\mathbf{h}) = \sigma(W_{4,\gamma}\mathbf{h} + b_{4,\gamma}) \odot (W_{5,\gamma}\mathbf{h} + b_{5,\gamma}), \quad (12)$$

where $\sigma(\cdot)$ represents the sigmoid activation function, producing gating values in the range of $[0, 1]$. Operator \odot denotes the element-wise Hadamard product, while $W_{4,\gamma}$, $W_{5,\gamma}$ are weight matrices and $b_{4,\gamma}$, $b_{5,\gamma}$ are biases. GLU allows the model to selectively filter features by modulating the influence of GRN's output on the primary input \mathbf{a} . In the absence of a context vector, GRN treats it as a zero vector. Additionally, dropout is employed prior to the gating layer and layer normalization to enhance the model's robustness and mitigate overfitting.

The gating mechanism in the customized TFT architecture enhances feature selection and model adaptability by dynamically controlling the flow of information at different layers. Unlike traditional gating mechanisms used in standard recurrent or attention-based networks, TFT employs specialized gating layers that regulate both temporal dependencies and input selection at a granular level. This allows the model to filter out irrelevant features while prioritizing informative ones, improving interpretability and robustness in time-series forecasting.

B. Variable Selection Networks

Variable selection networks play a crucial role in identifying the most relevant features for prediction, thereby mitigating the impact of noisy or irrelevant inputs. By focusing on the most salient variables, these networks enhance model performance and learning efficiency. Categorical variables are represented using entity embeddings, while continuous variables are subjected to linear transformations, yielding a k -dimensional vector that aligns with subsequent layers. Distinct variable selection networks process static, past, and future inputs, although their structure remains consistent across these types. For past inputs, the transformed input vectors $\mathbf{x}_t^{(j)} \in \mathbb{R}^k$ are aggregated into a flattened vector \mathbf{x}_t . The variable selection weights \mathbf{v}_t are computed by applying a GRN to \mathbf{x}_t and an external context vector \mathbf{c}_s , followed by a softmax activation:

$$\mathbf{v}_t = \text{softmax}(\text{GRN}_v(\mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{c}_s)). \quad (13)$$

Here, GRN_v denotes the GRN utilized for generating variable selection weights, and softmax function normalizes these weights. For static variables, the context vector \mathbf{c}_s is omitted, as static information is inherently available. Each variable $\mathbf{x}_t^{(j)}$ is processed through its own GRN to capture non-linear relationships:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_t^{(j)} = \text{GRN}_x^{(j)}(\mathbf{x}_t^{(j)}), \quad (14)$$

Fig. 3. Overview of the general TFT architecture.

where $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_t^{(j)}$ represents the processed feature vector for the j th variable. The final feature representation at each time step is obtained by applying weights and integrating these processed vectors:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_t = \sum_{j=1}^m v_t^{(j)} \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_t^{(j)}, \quad (15)$$

where $v_t^{(j)}$ is the j th element of the variable selection weight vector \mathbf{v}_t . This process ensures that only the most relevant features contribute to the model's predictions. The variable selection networks in TFT assign independent importance weights to static, past, and future inputs. Static variables are constant throughout the prediction window, shape the overall model behavior and are integrated at multiple stages to refine predictions. Past inputs capture historical patterns, whereas future inputs provide predictive guidance.

C. Static Covariates

Static covariates are incorporated into the TFT architecture through GRN encoders. These encoders produce four distinct context vectors: \mathbf{c}_s , \mathbf{c}_e , \mathbf{c}_c , and \mathbf{c}_h , each serving specific roles in the model's processing pipeline. Context vector \mathbf{c}_s is utilized to guide the selection of relevant temporal features, thus enhancing the model's ability to focus on pertinent data. Context vectors \mathbf{c}_c and \mathbf{c}_h facilitate the local processing of temporal features, ensuring that the model can adapt effectively to local patterns and trends. Context vector \mathbf{c}_e enriches the temporal features with static information, integrating static covariates into the temporal feature processing to provide a comprehensive understanding of the data. If $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}$ denotes the output of the variable selection network, the context for temporal variable selection is encoded as:

$$\mathbf{c}_s = \text{GRN}_{c_s}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}). \quad (16)$$

Here, GRN_{c_s} represents the GRN used to generate the context vector \mathbf{c}_s . These context vectors are employed at various stages within the temporal fusion decoder to ensure that static information is effectively integrated and utilized throughout the forecasting process, thereby contributing to improved model performance and accuracy.

D. Attention

TFT incorporates a self-attention mechanism to capture long-term dependencies across different time steps, significantly enhancing the model's interpretability compared to traditional multi-head attention utilized in transformer architectures. In a typical attention mechanism, the attention function scales values $\mathbf{V} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times d_v}$, where d_v denotes the dimensionality of the value vectors, based on the relationships between keys $\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times d_{attn}}$ and queries $\mathbf{Q} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times d_{attn}}$, where d_{attn} represents the dimensionality of both the key and query vectors, and N is the sequence length or the number of tokens in the input, as follows:

$$\text{Attention}(\mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{K}, \mathbf{V}) = A(\mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{K})\mathbf{V}. \quad (17)$$

$A()$ represents a normalization function. The scaled dot-product attention is a prevalent choice for $A()$:

$$A(\mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{K}) = \text{Softmax}\left(\frac{\mathbf{Q}\mathbf{K}^T}{\sqrt{d_{attn}}}\right). \quad (18)$$

To enhance the model's learning capacity, multi-head attention is employed in TFT. This approach utilizes multiple heads to capture different representation subspaces:

$$\text{MultiHead}(\mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{K}, \mathbf{V}) = [\mathbf{H}_1; \dots; \mathbf{H}_h]W_O, \quad (19)$$

where $\mathbf{H}_i = \text{Attention}(\mathbf{Q}W_i^Q, \mathbf{K}W_i^K, \mathbf{V}W_i^V)$ and W_i^Q, W_i^K, W_i^V are learned linear transformations. The final output W_O combines the attention outputs from each

head. The multi-head attention module within the TFT architecture is accompanied by residual connections and layer normalization, ensuring that information flows smoothly through the network. The integration of self-attention allows the model to adaptively weigh the contributions of different time steps.

Unlike conventional transformers, where multi-head attention primarily captures complex dependencies across tokens without inherent interpretability, TFT employs an attention mechanism explicitly designed to provide insights into the relative importance of past events and input features for forecasting. In TFT, multi-head attention is constrained to enhance interpretability, allowing attention weights to be directly analyzed to assess their contribution to the model’s predictions. This contrasts with standard transformer architectures, where attention patterns are often abstract and challenging to decipher. The enhanced interpretability of TFT is particularly advantageous in critical domains such as wireless communication and signal processing, where understanding feature importance is essential for reliable and explainable forecasting.

E. Decoder

The temporal fusion decoder refines the outputs from the attention mechanism and variable selection networks to generate the final predictions. The decoder combines processed features from previous layers to ensure robust forecasting and functions as follows:

$$\mathbf{y}_t = W_y \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_t + b_y, \quad (20)$$

where W_y is the weight matrix for the output layer, $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_t$ is the output from the previous layer, and b_y is the bias vector. The use of skip connections within the decoder facilitates the integration of information across multiple time steps, thus enhancing the model’s ability to leverage historical patterns for future predictions.

F. Technical Implementation of the Proposed TFT Adaptations

To clarify the concrete architectural innovations introduced in our method, we provide a detailed description of how each modification diverges from the standard TFT framework. In the baseline TFT, all inputs are treated as generic scalar covariates, and the output head is designed for conventional regression targets. In contrast, our formulation restructures both the input representation and the forecasting head to accommodate the geometric and temporal characteristics of directional data.

First, instead of feeding raw azimuth and elevation angles directly to the network, we transform each angular measurement (θ, ϕ) into its continuous representation using $(\sin \theta, \cos \theta, \sin \phi, \cos \phi)$, preventing discontinuities that the baseline TFT cannot naturally handle. These transformed coordinates are concatenated with additional signal-centric covariates—Doppler shift, received power, and sensor–target distance—which are not part of the standard TFT input space. Static attributes, such as antenna configuration and target class, are processed through embedding layers and routed into

the static context encoder, where, unlike the baseline TFT, they condition the internal gating functions via FiLM-style modulation to influence temporal reasoning across the full forecasting horizon.

For the temporal covariates, the baseline TFT relies on a uniform variable selection network applied identically across tasks. In our architecture, we modify this module to compute feature importance using a gated residual network that explicitly differentiates between slow-varying spatial descriptors and rapidly changing signal features. This adaptation allows the model to prioritize motion-related inputs—e.g., fading indicators or instantaneous angular velocity—during high-dynamic intervals, a capability absent in the baseline design. Within the sequence encoder, the LSTM and multi-head attention layers preserve the original TFT structure, but their behavior is influenced by the modified variable-selection outputs tailored to directional tracking scenarios. This enhancement enables more effective integration of short-term maneuvering cues and long-range temporal dependencies that are underutilized in the baseline when applied to angular forecasting.

Finally, we redesign the quantile forecasting head, which in the standard TFT predicts real-valued regression targets. Our version outputs quantiles in the transformed (\sin, \cos) coordinate space, and the predictions are mapped back to angles using

$$\theta = \text{atan2}(\sin \theta, \cos \theta),$$

where $\text{atan2}(\sin \theta, \cos \theta)$ returns angle θ in the interval $(-\pi, \pi]$. Training is guided by a direction-aware loss composed of: (i) quantile loss on the transformed outputs, (ii) an angular error penalty based on geodesic distance, and (iii) a temporal smoothness regularizer. None of these components exist in the baseline TFT, which lacks a mechanism for handling circular discontinuities or enforcing consistency across consecutive directional estimates.

G. Proposed Architecture and Hyperparameter Tuning

Hyperparameter tuning is crucial in neural networks as it directly influences model performance by managing the trade-off between underfitting and overfitting. Proper tuning enables the model to capture complex patterns while maintaining generalization to unseen data. Variables including learning rate, hidden layer size, and dropout rate control different aspects of the learning process, e.g., how quickly the model converges to how well it handles noise and variance. In our hyperparameter tuning process, several key factors are carefully analyzed to enhance the TFT model’s performance in forecasting. We implement grid search across specific ranges for each hyperparameter.

Hidden layer size is crucial, as it controls the model’s capacity to learn complex patterns. Smaller hidden layers (8 to 16 units) reduce the risk of overfitting in simpler datasets, while larger layers (up to 128 units) provide the model with greater flexibility to capture complex relationships but at the potential cost of increased overfitting. By testing a range from 8 to 64, we balance this trade-off, settling on 32 units to maintain a robust learning capacity without overcomplicating the model.

The hidden continuous size, responsible for handling continuous input features, was also varied between 8 and 64 units. Larger values for this hyperparameter allow the model to represent more intricate continuous relationships within the data, while smaller sizes may help avoid overfitting to noise. Our final selection of 16 units ensures the model remains expressive enough without introducing unnecessary complexity. Attention head size is another critical factor, directly influencing the model's ability to learn temporal relationships. Larger attention head sizes (up to 4) enable more parallel attention mechanisms to focus on different aspects of the data, improving the model's capacity to capture complex temporal dependencies, with the disadvantage of computational complexity. An attention head size of 2 offers an optimal balance between learning effectiveness and computational efficiency. Learning rate is a sensitive hyperparameter. A lower learning rate (0.001) provides a smoother, more gradual optimization path, minimizing the risk of overshooting minima, while higher learning rates (up to 0.1) can speed up convergence but at the risk of destabilizing the training process. Through experimentation, we identify 0.001 as the ideal rate, ensuring both stable training and efficient learning. Finally, in our analysis, dropout rate was varied from 0.1 to 0.3 to mitigate overfitting. A dropout rate of 0.1 proves sufficient to regularize the model, ensuring robust performance without sacrificing learning capacity. This modest dropout level cooperates well with the relatively small hidden sizes we selected.

IV. NUMERICAL RESULTS

We assess the angular error using multiple metrics to capture different aspects of prediction accuracy, reporting results both jointly and separately for elevation (θ) and azimuth (ϕ) angles. The mean absolute error (MAE) measures the average magnitude of errors and is computed independently for each angle as:

$$\text{MAE}_\theta = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=1}^k \left| \hat{\theta}_i - \theta_i \right|, \quad (21)$$

$$\text{MAE}_\phi = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=1}^k \left| \hat{\phi}_i - \phi_i \right|, \quad (22)$$

For completeness, a combined MAE metric can be computed by summing the absolute errors for both angles:

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=1}^k \left(\left| \hat{\theta}_i - \theta_i \right| + \left| \hat{\phi}_i - \phi_i \right| \right). \quad (23)$$

To account for variance and emphasize larger errors, we use root mean square error (RMSE) calculated separately as:

$$\text{RMSE}_\theta = \sqrt{\frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=1}^k (\hat{\theta}_i - \theta_i)^2}, \quad (24)$$

$$\text{RMSE}_\phi = \sqrt{\frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=1}^k (\hat{\phi}_i - \phi_i)^2}, \quad (25)$$

with the combined form expressed as:

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=1}^k \left((\hat{\theta}_i - \theta_i)^2 + (\hat{\phi}_i - \phi_i)^2 \right)}. \quad (26)$$

Finally, we incorporate symmetric mean absolute percentage error (SMAPE), which scales the absolute errors relative to the average of the predicted and actual values, computed independently by:

$$\text{SMAPE}_\theta = \frac{100}{k} \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{|\hat{\theta}_i - \theta_i|}{\frac{1}{2} (|\hat{\theta}_i| + |\theta_i|)}, \quad (27)$$

$$\text{SMAPE}_\phi = \frac{100}{k} \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{|\hat{\phi}_i - \phi_i|}{\frac{1}{2} (|\hat{\phi}_i| + |\phi_i|)}, \quad (28)$$

and combined as:

$$\text{SMAPE} = \frac{100}{k} \sum_{i=1}^k \left(\frac{|\hat{\theta}_i - \theta_i|}{\frac{1}{2} (|\hat{\theta}_i| + |\theta_i|)} + \frac{|\hat{\phi}_i - \phi_i|}{\frac{1}{2} (|\hat{\phi}_i| + |\phi_i|)} \right). \quad (29)$$

Fig. 4. Validation of independent target recognition and tracking performance.

A. Tracking Performance

First, we train our model on 30,000 samples, 10,000 for each target type. Fig. 4 presents the comparison between the actual and predicted values of the angular variables θ and ϕ during the model training phase over 200 time steps. The solid blue line represents the actual angles, while the dashed red line shows the values predicted by the TFT model. The close alignment between the two indicates the model's accuracy in capturing angular movement patterns. Notably, TFT effectively identifies peaks and directional shifts, maintaining robust performance regardless of the target's movement speed or frequency of directional changes.

B. Forecasting Ability

Upon the training phase, we validate our model on various occasions and conditions. Our model demonstrates low quantile error and minimal variation between the 10th ($\hat{\theta}_{0.1}$, $\hat{\phi}_{0.1}$) and 90th ($\hat{\theta}_{0.9}$, $\hat{\phi}_{0.9}$) percentile predictions, reflecting low uncertainty in the DoA estimations. The 50th percentile ($\hat{\theta}_{0.5}$, $\hat{\phi}_{0.5}$) is taken as the predicted DoA for subsequent analysis. Table II presents the average error metrics for angular predictions over 100 samples for the target categories we investigate. The results indicate that the model performs exceptionally well in all target types, with the MAE for UAV, car, and pedestrian being below 0.1° on average. Similarly, RMSE shows a low range, confirming the accuracy of the model in estimating angular positions. Pedestrian targets exhibit the lowest average errors, suggesting that the model captures their movements with high precision, due to their more predictable trajectories compared to other target types. SMAPE remains consistently low for all targets. In particular, the accuracy of the predictions for both θ and ϕ is comparable, demonstrating the model's ability to effectively interpret and predict angular pairs, thus enabling accurate 3D positioning of the targets.

TABLE II
AVERAGE ERROR FOR 1 POSITION FORECAST OVER 100 SAMPLES.

Target	θ ($^\circ$)			ϕ ($^\circ$)		
	MAE	RMSE	SMAPE	MAE	RMSE	SMAPE
Pedestrian	0.03 $^\circ$	0.04 $^\circ$	0.05%	0.06 $^\circ$	0.07 $^\circ$	0.04%
Car	0.08 $^\circ$	0.1 $^\circ$	0.08%	0.1 $^\circ$	0.11 $^\circ$	0.1%
UAV	0.06 $^\circ$	0.07 $^\circ$	0.07%	0.08 $^\circ$	0.08 $^\circ$	0.09%

C. Ablation Study of Architectural Modifications

To quantify the contribution of each proposed component, we conducted an ablation study by starting from the full proposed TFT model and progressively removing one modification at a time. The evaluated components include: (i) sine-cosine angular encoding, (ii) the direction-aware loss function, and (iii) the refined variable selection mechanism. Table III summarizes the results in terms of MAE, RMSE, and detection probability. All results were obtained under the car-movement scenario at 20 dB SNR, using 50,000 samples consistently across all model variants to ensure experimental fairness.

The complete proposed model achieves the best performance, with an MAE of 0.08° , RMSE of 0.1° , and detection probability of 98%. The removal of the sine-cosine encoding degrades performance substantially (MAE 0.9° , RMSE 1.5° , detection probability 93%), showcasing the importance of preserving angular periodicity in directional prediction tasks. Removing the direction-aware loss leads to a noticeable decline in accuracy (MAE 0.5° , RMSE 1°), indicating that explicitly penalizing angular deviations improves regression stability. Similarly, excluding the refined variable selection mechanism increases error (MAE 0.4° , RMSE 0.5°) and slightly reduces detection probability, demonstrating the benefit of structured feature selection within the temporal modeling pipeline. For reference, the baseline TFT without any of the proposed

TABLE III
ABLATION STUDY OF PROPOSED TFT MODIFICATIONS

Model Variant	MAE	RMSE	Detection Prob.
Proposed TFT	0.08 $^\circ$	0.1 $^\circ$	98%
- Sin/Cos Encoding	0.9 $^\circ$	1.5 $^\circ$	93%
- Direction-Aware Loss	0.5 $^\circ$	1 $^\circ$	95%
- Refined Variable Selection	0.4 $^\circ$	0.5 $^\circ$	96%
Baseline TFT	2.84 $^\circ$	3.92 $^\circ$	91%

modifications exhibits significantly higher error (MAE 2.84° , RMSE 3.92°) and lower detection probability (91%), indicating that the observed improvements arise from the combined effect of the introduced architectural adaptations rather than the base TFT framework alone.

D. Sensitivity Analysis on Direction-Change Probability

To assess the robustness of our model to variations in motion behavior, we conducted a sensitivity analysis by varying the probability of direction change in the simulated trajectories. While the baseline simulation used a 30% probability of direction change every 5 seconds, we evaluated the model under two additional conditions: 10% (less dynamic) and 50% (more erratic). This analysis was performed using the car target class, which serves as the baseline due to its representative motion complexity. The results, summarized in Table IV, reflect the combined angular error across both elevation (θ) and azimuth (ϕ) for a single target over one prediction horizon. The model's performance remains stable across all three scenarios, with only minor fluctuations in the error metrics.

TABLE IV
SENSITIVITY OF MODEL PERFORMANCE TO DIRECTION-CHANGE PROBABILITY

Probability	MAE ($^\circ$)	RMSE ($^\circ$)	SMAPE (%)
10%	0.05	0.06	0.04
30%	0.08	0.1	0.08
50%	0.16	0.27	0.24

E. Multiple Signals Recognition

In Fig. 5, we evaluate the overall prediction performance of the TFT model, specifically evaluating its ability to distinguish between multiple simultaneous received signals from different targets. This evaluation utilizes 1,000 randomly generated angles, with the frequency of each target indicated on the right y-axis. The time-series data are extracted from multi-target simulation scenarios, where each target is assigned a persistent ground-truth identifier throughout the entire sequence. During preprocessing, these identifiers are used to group observations into coherent per-target time series, ensuring that each sequence corresponds to a single, consistently tracked target across all time steps.

The plot juxtaposes the predicted angles against the actual angles for three different target types, illustrating the average elevation position of each target. The results clearly demonstrate the effectiveness of the model in tracking multiple distinct targets, each exhibiting unique movement patterns. The TFT model successfully follows their independent trajectories,

accurately forecasting their behaviors over time. This ability to manage complex scenarios with varying dynamics underscores the robustness and precision of the TFT model in multi-target tracking applications.

Fig. 5. Multiple target recognition validation.

F. Performance Dependency on Input Size

In subsequent analysis, we evaluate our model across datasets of varying dimensions to observe its performance sensitivity and to assess how scalability affects prediction accuracy and efficiency. This analysis also includes comparison models, allowing us to comprehensively benchmark the TFT’s performance in a broader context. As shown in Table V, the transformer shows a notable improvement in accuracy as the sample size increases, highlighting its ability to leverage larger datasets effectively and narrowing the performance gap with the proposed TFT model. However, the TFT consistently outperforms the transformer and the RNN-based models in all sample sizes, maintaining superior accuracy and shorter processing times.

G. Detection Probability

Detection probability is a critical metric for evaluating the performance of detection algorithms, especially in noisy environments. In our analysis, we calculate the detection probability as the ratio of correctly detected targets to the total number of targets. Fig. 6 presents the detection probability for various SNR values. At -10 dB, the mean detection probability is 0.89, with a median of 0.85. The variance is relatively low, as reflected in the spread of the boxplot. At 0 dB, the mean and median improve to 0.95 and 0.93, respectively, with a reduced variance, indicating that the model begins to achieve more reliable detection as the noise level decreases. At high SNR (10-20 dB), the proposed model achieves near-perfect performance with a mean of 0.99 and a median of 0.98. The variance drops to an impressively low level, confirming that the algorithm consistently detects signals with minimal error in high SNR scenarios. As expected, the

mean detection probability improves with increasing SNR, despite the system’s robustness to noise even at low SNR values. The dashed line represents the median, which closely follows the mean. The proximity between the two indicates that the detection performance is consistent between samples without significant outliers.

Fig. 6. Detection probability vs SNR.

H. Comparison Against State-of-the-Art for Multiple Prediction Horizons

A comparison of our proposed TFT with state-of-the-art neural network architectures, including long short-term memory models (LSTMs) [55], gated recurrent unit models (GRUs) [56] and conventional transformers [46], reveals significant distinctions. Classical model-based tracking methods, including the EKF and UKF, were considered during preliminary evaluations. However, abrupt maneuvering, non-linear trajectory evolution, and time-varying signal propagation effects introduced modeling mismatches that limited performance. Consequently, the experimental evaluation focuses on data-driven sequence models that are better suited to learning complex temporal dynamics directly from the observed signals and are more closely aligned with the characteristics of the dataset and the objectives of the proposed framework.

Our comparative analysis utilizes random target types sourced from our dataset. All baseline models used for comparison were independently tuned and trained using a consistent and carefully controlled evaluation framework. We applied grid search to optimize model-specific hyperparameters based on validation set performance using the same quantile regression loss as the proposed method. The tuning procedure included variations in hidden size, number of layers, learning rate, and dropout, with early stopping employed to mitigate overfitting. For the LSTM, the best-performing setup used two layers with 128 hidden units, striking a balance between model capacity and generalization. The GRU achieved optimal performance with two layers and 64 hidden units, benefiting from a simpler architecture while effectively capturing temporal dependencies. The Transformer baseline

TABLE V
MODEL PERFORMANCE ACROSS DIFFERENT SAMPLE SIZES FOR EACH TARGET TYPE ON 1 HORIZON.

Model	5k Samples		10k Samples		20k Samples		35k Samples		50k Samples	
	RMSE	Time	RMSE	Time	RMSE	Time	RMSE	Time	RMSE	Time
TFT	0.09°	0.1 ms	0.08°	0.1 ms	0.09°	0.3 ms	0.09°	0.5 ms	0.10°	0.7 ms
Transformer	0.31°	0.3 ms	0.18°	0.52 ms	0.17°	0.58 ms	0.18°	0.6 ms	0.18°	0.9 ms
GRU	0.9°	0.57 ms	0.73°	0.74 ms	1.15°	0.84 ms	1.14°	1.18 ms	1.36°	1.37 ms
LSTM	1.1°	0.74 ms	1°	0.87 ms	1.35°	0.95 ms	1.44°	1.25 ms	1.47°	1.58 ms

employed four encoder layers with eight attention heads, a model dimension of 128, and appropriate positional encodings for time-series data. All models were trained under identical conditions, including the use of the Adam optimizer, a fixed batch size, and a learning rate scheduler.

Fig. 7. Comparison analysis on accuracy performance.

As shown in Fig. 7, the proposed model exhibits exceptional performance, achieving an RMSE of 0.08° at a prediction horizon of 1 while accounting for three target types. Although error metrics experience a slight increase with longer prediction horizons, they remain remarkably low, with the RMSE remaining below 0.5° for up to 7 horizons and below 1° for up to 11 horizons. These findings highlight the model's ability to sustain impressive accuracy across a wide range of forecasting horizons, ensuring robust performance even for extended predictions. The transformer architecture follows closely behind in performance, while both the GRU and LSTM models demonstrate significantly inferior results. Notably, the proposed TFT achieves nearly 10 times higher accuracy than RNN-based models for extended forecasts, underscoring its effectiveness in this context.

We also provide a comparison analysis on the detection probability of our TFT-based model against three state-of-the-art models. Figure 8 illustrates the detection probability across SNR levels ranging from -10 dB to 20 dB.

The proposed model achieves the highest detection probability across all SNR conditions. At low SNR (-10 dB to 0 dB), the TFT exhibits significantly greater robustness compared to the baseline models, maintaining reliable target detection

Fig. 8. Detection probability versus SNR for the proposed TFT model and three state-of-the-art neural architectures (Transformer, LSTM, GRU).

even in high-noise regimes. In contrast, the GRU and LSTM architectures demonstrate substantially lower detection rates, showing reduced stability in noisy environments due to their limited ability to extract long-range temporal dependencies from the array snapshots. The Transformer baseline performs better than the recurrent models but still falls short of the TFT, especially in the low-SNR region. This performance gap highlights the benefit of the TFT's gating mechanisms, variable selection layers, and multi-horizon attention, which collectively enable more effective spatiotemporal feature extraction. As SNR increases beyond 10 dB, all models approach near-perfect detection probability; however, the TFT maintains a consistent advantage, reflecting superior convergence behavior and generalization capability.

I. Complexity Analysis

Fig. 9 presents a detailed comparison of prediction times in 15 prediction horizons. The results clearly demonstrate that the TFT consistently outperforms both RNN-based models and conventional transformers in terms of speed. At a prediction horizon of 1, the TFT completes the predictions in just 0.1 milliseconds (ms), significantly faster than the transformer's 0.35 ms. This speed advantage becomes even more pronounced with longer horizons, as the TFT is 5 times faster than the transformer at a horizon of 15. In contrast, the complexity of the LSTM model results in prediction times that are up to 7 times slower, whereas the GRU performs better, although it still demonstrates a notable speed deficiency.

The proposed TFT model demonstrates a computational complexity of 4.33 million FLOPs and includes 7.5×10^4 trainable parameters, making it an exceptionally efficient option for time series forecasting. In contrast, the GRU has 8.5×10^4 trainable parameters, whereas the LSTM contains 11×10^4 . This efficiency in comparison to the LSTM is attributed to the GRU’s simplified gating mechanism, which also leads to a reduction in computational complexity. On the other hand, the transformer architecture has a significantly larger model capacity, with nearly 30×10^4 trainable parameters, resulting in a higher computational overhead of 6.5 million FLOPs. Although the Transformer baseline has a higher parameter count than the proposed TFT model, all architectures were independently tuned using the same training, validation, and early-stopping procedure to ensure appropriate capacity selection. The Transformer configuration reported in this work corresponds to the best-performing variant on the validation set, and no systematic evidence of overfitting was observed. Consequently, the performance differences reported in Fig. 7 are not attributable to parameter scaling effects, but rather reflect differences in how the respective architectures process temporal information and input features under the same experimental conditions.

Fig. 9. Comparison analysis on time-for-forecast performance.

J. Interpretability

Tables VI and VII present the importance of the variables for the encoder and decoder components of the TFT, highlighting the features that most significantly influence the model performance. In the encoder, the most critical variables are target type, accounting for 30%, and monitored angles, contributing 28%, highlighting the importance of understanding both the target’s nature and its angular position. Furthermore, the monitored angle velocity plays a significant role in 20%, capturing the dynamics of the target movement. Other key features include the distance from the sensors at 10%, the Doppler shift at 8%, and the received power at 4%. These measurements demonstrate that the encoder relies mainly on spatial and

angular information to effectively predict the trajectories of different target types.

TABLE VI
ENCODER VARIABLES IMPORTANCE.

Encoder Variable	Importance (%)
Target Type	30
Monitored Angles	28
Monitored Angle Velocity	20
Distance to Sensors	10
Doppler Shift	8
Received Power	4

In the decoder, the importance of the variable changes notably, with the past angle velocity monitored accounting for a substantial 80%. This emphasis suggests that understanding the recent motion dynamics of the targets is paramount for accurate future predictions. Time (20%) is also significant, as it helps the model to account for temporal dependencies in the prediction process. This contrast between encoder and decoder variable importance underscores the TFT’s design, where the encoder focuses on capturing the features of the input data to understand the current state, while the decoder leverages past motion dynamics to forecast future behaviors effectively.

TABLE VII
DECODER VARIABLES IMPORTANCE.

Decoder Variable	Importance (%)
Monitored Past Angle Velocity	80
Time Index	20

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE EXTENSIONS

This study explores the application of the TFT model for multi-horizon target localization forecasting, emphasizing its ability to predict 3D positioning with high accuracy across extended time horizons. A comprehensive evaluation of the proposed model using a simulation-based framework is presented. This approach allows precise control over signal parameters, target motion, and environmental factors, enabling systematic analysis of model performance under diverse and repeatable conditions. The advantages and contributions of using the TFT architecture for DoA estimation are thoroughly examined, with the proposed model being carefully optimized and tuned. Through extensive experimentation, we demonstrated that TFT consistently outperforms state-of-the-art models, achieving superior accuracy and speed across various prediction horizons. TFT achieved a remarkable RMSE as low as 0.08° for shorter horizons, with rapid response times of 0.1 milliseconds, underscoring its suitability for real-time forecasting tasks. The computational efficiency of the proposed TFT model highlights its potential for practical time-sensitive applications. Future research could explore the development of hybrid models; e.g., the integration of convolutional layers with the TFT could improve the model’s ability to capture local spatial dependencies in time series data. Leveraging transfer learning techniques, where TFT is trained on large, general datasets and

later fine-tuned for specific tasks, could improve the model's adaptability and reduce the need for extensive hyperparameter tuning when applied to new domains. Such advancements would not only enhance TFT's capabilities in array signal processing but also pave the way for comprehensive real-world applications in various fields. To that end, we acknowledge that validation with real-world antenna array measurements is a critical next step, and we plan to pursue this in future work to further assess the model's practical applicability.

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